

The Role of Organizational Culture in Enhancing Administrative Performance among School Principals: An Analytical Study of the Opinions of a Sample of Private School Principals in Erbil

Hassan Hamad Abdulla¹, Dr. Hoshmand Rafiq Ibrahim², Dr. Saman Sidqi Hamad Ameen³

¹Central Education Directorate/Ministry of Education/Kurdistan Regional Government-Iraq

²College of Administration and Economics Salahaddin University- Erbil/ Kurdistan Regional -Iraq

³Erbil Technical Administrative College, Erbil Polytechnic University/ Kurdistan Regional -Iraq

ABSTRACT: This study aims to determine the role of organizational culture in enhancing administrative performance among private school principals in Erbil. Organizational culture serves as the independent variable through three dimensions: teamwork, norms and laws, innovation and creativity. Administrative performance serves as the dependent variable through three dimensions: decision-making, guidance and control, planning and organization. These dimensions directly influence how principals make decisions and how they interact with teachers and students. The study relied on a descriptive analytical approach by collecting and analyzing the opinions of a sample of private school principals. The variables were described, and the relationships and impact between them were analyzed. The field of study comprised private schools in Erbil city center. The study sample consisted of (80) respondents out of a total of (110) school principals. The hypotheses were tested using statistical methods using the computer program (SPSS V.24). The study leads to a set of main conclusions that there is a critical and spiritual relationship between the dimensions of organizational culture and the dimensions of managerial performance Private schools in Erbil. The study includes a collection of recommendations to encourage principals to identify the type of positive culture in their schools and work on developing it as a culture that supports creativity and collective action. and the issue, and the initiative.

KEYWORDS: Organizational Culture, Administrative Performance, School Principals, Private Schools, Erbil City.

INTRODUCTION

Educational institutions are among the most important pillars of societal development, bearing the responsibility of preparing a generation that is aware and capable of keeping pace with rapid changes. In this context, the administrative performance of school principals has become a vital element in determining the quality of educational outcomes. The more effective and efficient a principal is in managing their school's affairs, the more positively this is reflected in the performance of teachers and students.

Despite the importance of material and technological factors, recent studies have proven that organizational culture is the hidden engine of institutional success. It forms the value and behavioral framework that governs the actions of individuals within the organization and directly affects their level of commitment, productivity, and job satisfaction. In the educational work environment, organizational culture translates into a set of shared values and beliefs about how to achieve goals, how to deal with challenges, and how to shape relationships between members of the teaching and administrative staff.

This study aims to highlight the importance and necessity of organizational culture and its impact on enhancing the administrative performance of private school principals in Erbil, Kurdistan Region- Iraq.

1. General Framework and Methodology of the Research:

This research outlines the general framework, methodology, statistical tools used for data analysis and hypothesis testing, and the research population and sample, as follows:

1.1 Research Problem

Despite the increasing importance of organizational culture, many institutions still face challenges in its effective implementation, which affects the quality of their administrative performance. The study problem is addressed in the following question: What role does organizational culture play in enhancing administrative performance in private schools? This question leads to the following sub-questions:

- What is the current state of organizational culture in private schools in Erbil from the perspective of school principals?

“The Role of Organizational Culture in Enhancing Administrative Performance among School Principals: An Analytical Study of the Opinions of a Sample of Private School Principals in Erbil”

- What is the level of administrative performance of private school principals in Erbil?
- What is the relationship between organizational culture and administrative performance among private school principals in Erbil?
- Are there statistically significant differences in the relationship between organizational culture and administrative performance attributable to the demographic variables (such as age, experience, and educational qualifications) of the principals? Given the importance of economic intelligence in general, and the importance of strategic decision-making in particular, the need to address this issue becomes apparent. This research seeks to answer the following questions:
 1. What is the nature of the relationship between organizational culture, in its various dimensions, and managerial performance?
 2. What is the impact of the dimensions of organizational culture on managerial performance?

2.1. Research Objectives:

This study aims to achieve the following objectives:

1. To analyze the theoretical and applied relationship between organizational culture and administrative performance.
2. To determine the extent to which private school principals understand the concept of organizational culture and its importance in the work environment.
3. To identify the most prominent features of the prevailing organizational culture in private schools in Erbil, such as work values, communication styles, and reward systems.
4. To analyze the impact of different dimensions of organizational culture on the administrative performance of school principals, with the aim of identifying which cultural aspects positively or negatively affect their performance.
5. To provide practical recommendations to contribute to the development of organizational culture in these schools, thereby supporting and improving the administrative performance of principals and ultimately leading to improved quality of education.

3.1. Research Hypotheses:

The research hypotheses are as follows:

First Hypothesis: Nullifying Hypothesis (H0): There is no statistically significant positive correlation between organizational culture and administrative performance at a significance level of 0.05.

Alternative Hypothesis (H1): There is statistically significant positive correlation between organizational culture and administrative performance at a significance level of 0.05.

Second Hypothesis: Nullifying Hypothesis (H0): There is no statistically significant positive correlation between the

dimensions of organizational culture and administrative performance at a significance level of 0.05.

-Alternative Hypothesis (H1): There is a statistically significant positive correlation between the dimensions of organizational culture and administrative performance at a significance level of 0.05.

-Third Hypothesis: Nullifying Hypothesis (H0): Organizational culture does not have a statistically significant positive effect on administrative performance at a significance level of 0.05. Alternative hypothesis (H1): Organizational culture has a statistically significant positive impact on managerial performance at a significance level of 0.05.

4.1 Significance of the Research:

The significance of this research stems from studying the role of organizational culture in enhancing the administrative performance of school principals in private schools in Erbil, Kurdistan Region, Iraq. This research represents a valuable contribution to enriching the knowledge of other researchers in the field of organizational culture and administrative performance.

- Scientific Significance: The study contributes to enriching the academic literature related to organizational culture and administrative performance, and offers new insights into the relationship between them.

-Theoretical Significance: This study contributes to the theoretical framework for understanding the role of organizational culture in enhancing the administrative performance of school principals, focusing on private schools in Erbil, Kurdistan Region, Iraq. Furthermore, the study aims to enrich Iraqi, Kurdish, and word libraries with additional research on the role of organizational culture in enhancing the administrative performance of school principals in private schools in Erbil, Kurdistan Region, Iraq.

5.1. Scope of the Study:

The study was defined by the following temporal, spatial, human, and cognitive parameters:

- **Temporal Scope:** The period during which data will be collected and analyzed for this study is from April 1, 2025, to November 1, 2025.
- **Spatial Scope:** Private schools in Erbil, Kurdistan Region, Iraq.
- **Human Scope:** A sample of principals from private schools in Erbil.
- **Cognitive (Thematic) Scope:** The role of organizational culture in enhancing the administrative performance of school principals.

6.1 Research Methodology:

The research adopted descriptive and analytical methodologies to measure the impact of strategic leadership on economic sustainability.

“The Role of Organizational Culture in Enhancing Administrative Performance among School Principals: An Analytical Study of the Opinions of a Sample of Private School Principals in Erbil”

-Methods Used: Quantitative and qualitative data analysis using software such as SPSS to analyze questionnaires and test hypotheses.

-Data Collection Tools: Questionnaires and literature reviews.

-Research Population: Private schools in Erbil, Kurdistan Region, Iraq. - Sample size: (80) participants from private school principals in Erbil.

7.1 Research sources for data collection:

Information and data for the research were collected from primary and secondary sources, the World Wide Web (Internet), and library resources. There are approximately

(110) private schools in Erbil registered with the Ministry of Education/Kurdistan Regional Government - Iraq.

8.1. Research Model

A hypothetical model was built to demonstrate the possibility of providing a suitable environment for private schools in Erbil, Kurdistan Region, Iraq, through three dimensions of organizational culture (teamwork, norms and laws, innovation and creativity) and three dimensions of administrative performance (decision-making, guidance and control, planning and organization), and to demonstrate the extent of their impact between the two research variables and express the extent of their consistency with the work environment in private schools, as shown in Figure(1).

Figure (1) Research Model
Source: Prepared by researchers

Correlation relationship \longleftrightarrow Influence relationship \longrightarrow

2.THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

1.2 The Concept of Organizational Culture

The concept of organizational culture is a modern one addressed in management literature. This concept encompasses the knowledge, ideas, and values that emerge among the members of a society (Al-Atabi, 2014, p.13).

Organizational culture is defined as a set of values, beliefs, practices, and customs that school administrators practice, which regulate their relationships, functions, interactions, and achievements within the educational system. It was measured through teachers' responses to a questionnaire on organizational culture (Al-Marqatan, 2020, p. 11). The concept of organizational culture has been transferred to the educational and general fields, particularly schools, as social organizations with a unique character that distinguishes them from others. Each school has its own culture with a specific

system of complex values that govern social relationships among individuals, such as customs and laws through which work ethics are expressed. The importance of this concept stems from its role as a framework for defining employee behavior and the behavioral and relationship models that should be followed and guided by it (Muqabala, 2022, p. 181).

Abu Kosh (2024, p. 174) defines it as the prevailing values that school principals contribute to shaping through their interaction with the school community. These values include teamwork, establishing humane relationships within the school community, encouraging innovation and renewal, and achieving fairness among school staff.

Researchers define organizational culture as the spirit that animates the school and determines the nature of

work within it. The principal is considered the primary architect of this culture.

2.2 The Importance of Organizational Culture

Organizational culture affects all aspects of business, especially in the field of educational administration. Al-Shammari and Al-Anzi (2022, p.183) summarize the importance of organizational culture in several points as follows:

- It establishes an organizational identity, unites its members, and distinguishes them from others.
- It fosters loyalty and a sense of belonging to the organization.
- It achieves organizational stability.
- It cultivates awareness of surrounding events and issues.
- It identifies areas of common interest.
- It helps determine administrative priorities.
- It anticipates administrative behavior patterns in difficult situations and crises.
- It promotes desired leadership and guidance roles.
- It provides a self-monitoring mechanism for desired behavior and attitude patterns.
- It establishes a framework for teachers that helps them understand the organization's directions and activities and guides them toward appropriate behavior.

3.3 Types of Organizational Cultures

Researchers and writers specializing in organizational culture have differed in defining specific types, relying on a range of divisions and classifications. Among the most important of these is Harrison's classification, which divides organizational culture into four types (Abbas, 2022, p. 12):

1. **Power Culture:** A power culture typically derives its strength from a single source. This source is the deployment of a specialized function aimed at controlling and influencing all aspects of the organization (a spiderweb). The effectiveness of this culture depends on mutual trust between leaders and employees, as well as on personal, interpersonal communication. Power is distributed in this culture, but there is a strong sense of cooperation between the organization and its members to achieve shared goals. This type is prevalent in relatively small and modern organizations.
2. **Role Culture:** The strength of a role culture lies in functional specialization. A role culture is viewed as a set of pillars managed and coordinated by a limited group of executives. Rules and procedures govern the internal environment, and this type is most successful in stable environments. This type can be observed in bureaucratic organizations.
3. **People-Centered Culture:** This culture is based on the collective participation of individuals in decision-making. It prioritizes individuals and prevents any single individual from dominating the rest. This type of culture is often observed in small, technically-oriented organizations.

4. **Task-Centered Culture:** This culture focuses on task completion. Power is distributed and dispersed, relying more on expertise than on position or personal influence. It typically develops in organizations that focus on specific projects, where dedicated teams are assigned to complete them. These teams are characterized by flexibility, alignment, harmony, and relative autonomy in decision-making and shared responsibilities.

Habashi (2024, p. 30) noted that organizational culture can be either strong or weak. In a strong culture, employees adopt the same beliefs, principles, and values as the organization. Organizations with strong cultures achieve significant success because they promote the alignment of goals, contribute to stability, commitment, and high employee engagement, and lead to lower employee turnover.

4.2 Organizational Culture in the Field of Administrative Practices:

Administrative practices encompass the actions and duties performed by the principal within the school, which lead to the achievement of the school's defined educational goals through the best educational and administrative means. Among the administrative tasks and functions performed by the principal in the school are planning, organizing, coordinating, directing, supervising, monitoring, and evaluating (Alian, 2012, p. 31).

(Ahbeil et al., 2022, p.30) indicated that among the responsibilities of the school principal, as an educational leader, is identifying all the educational and administrative competencies present in the school, distributing responsibilities among them according to their aptitudes and abilities, placing the right person in the right position, working to raise the professional and technical level of all staff members, encouraging them to seek knowledge, undergo training and self-development, and continue experimenting, researching, and innovating to perform their duties to the best of their ability. This includes planning and implementing successful educational situations and serious educational experiments that benefit students and the surrounding environment.

Organizational culture plays a crucial role in enhancing the administrative performance of private school principals by providing a positive and motivating work environment. Organizational culture is the set of shared values, beliefs, principles, and behaviors that define how individuals work and interact within the school. When this culture is strong and positive, it contributes to the efficient and effective achievement of educational and administrative goals.

5.2 The Concept of Administrative Performance

Before we delve into the concept of administrative performance, it is important to define it as: “An expression of the degree to which an individual, team, or organization

“The Role of Organizational Culture in Enhancing Administrative Performance among School Principals: An Analytical Study of the Opinions of a Sample of Private School Principals in Erbil”

achieves its planned goals efficiently and effectively” (Al-Ahmadi, 2018, p. 434).

It encompasses the responsibilities, duties, and tasks that an individual must perform within their job position in the institution where they work (Al-Akouri, 2024, p. 462). Many experts in administrative work believe that administrative performance is one of the administrative variables that impacts the morale of the manager and their staff. There should be shared perspectives between the manager and their staff regarding the tasks expected to be accomplished, in addition to defining school objectives (educational/pedagogical). Furthermore, the manager should support all members of the school community—students, teachers, and staff—to encourage and motivate them to fulfill their roles (Kamel, 2029, p. 44).

6.2 Objectives of Enhancing Administrative Performance

Every enhancement process has its own specific objectives; however, the overall goal of any The process of enhancing performance involves improving school principals. Al-Afad and Al-Najjar (2022, p. 41) stated that the objectives of enhancing school principals include:

- Improving educational outcomes for students by enhancing the quality of teaching and leadership.
- Integrating policies, practices, standards, and procedures that link the school's goals and objectives.
- Establishing agreed-upon performance expectations and performance measurement processes based on these expectations.
- Focusing on the professional development of each school.

7.2 Challenges in enhancing the administrative performance of school principals

Hassanin et al. (2022, pp. 10-23) identified several obstacles facing school administrations that hinder the development of principals' administrative performance, including:

1. **Technical:** This refers to obstacles related to the educational process, such as the low performance level of some teachers due to professional, personal, or psychological reasons, which negatively impacts the school's effectiveness and outcomes. It also includes deficiencies in teachers' professional preparation and qualification levels, forcing principals to rely on unqualified or non-specialized individuals to perform certain tasks, or to delegate responsibilities to teachers whose qualifications and abilities the principal trusts.
2. **Administrative:** This refers to obstacles related to the administrative aspect, including:

- Insufficient financial resources to fulfill the tasks and responsibilities of the school principal.
- Inadequate availability or unsuitability of school buildings and necessary facilities.
- Weak or nonexistent administrative skills among some school administrators.
- Overcrowded classrooms with students who have exceeded the school's reasonable admission age.

3. DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS AND DATA QUALITY TESTS

To achieve the objectives of this study, a range of appropriate statistical methods were employed. The five-point Likert scale was used to measure participants' attitudes and opinions, while the arithmetic mean and standard deviation were used for descriptive data analysis. Cronbach's alpha test was also adopted to ensure the reliability of the questionnaire instrument, in addition to using Pearson's correlation coefficient and regression analysis to examine the nature of the relationships between the variables under investigation.

1.3 Internal Reliability Test of the Questionnaire (Consistency):

Reliability testing is a fundamental step to ensure the reliability of the results obtained in any questionnaire-based study. Reliability reflects the ability of a measurement instrument to produce similar and stable results when re-administered to the same individuals under similar conditions. One of the most prominent statistical methods used in this field is Cronbach's alpha coefficient, which is considered one of the most important indicators of internal consistency. The value of this coefficient ranges from 0 to 1, where values below 0.60 indicate weak internal consistency, while values between 0.60 and 0.80 reflect an acceptable to good level of reliability. Values above 0.80 indicate a high level of reliability, and a value of 1 represents perfect reliability, as explained by Cronbach (1951).

To determine the effectiveness of the research instrument used in this study, Cronbach's alpha coefficient was calculated for each of the two variables, in addition to the overall reliability coefficient for the questionnaire. These results are presented in detail in Table 1, showing the coefficient values for each variable and the number of items comprising it. This step is essential to ensure the questionnaire's validity and to confirm that all its items accurately and consistently measure the targeted concepts.

Table (2) Cronbach's Alpha test for measuring questionnaire reliability

Form paragraphs	Cronbach's alpha coefficient	Number of paragraphs
Organizational culture	0.801	12
Administrative performance	0.769	12

Source: Prepared by researchers using SPSS

“The Role of Organizational Culture in Enhancing Administrative Performance among School Principals: An Analytical Study of the Opinions of a Sample of Private School Principals in Erbil”

Table (1) shows that Cronbach's alpha coefficient for the organizational culture questionnaire was (0.801) with 12 items, while Cronbach's alpha coefficient for the managerial performance questionnaire was (0.769) with 12 items as well. These values indicate that both questionnaires

have good to excellent reliability, reflecting the instrument's high reliability in data collection and its ability to produce consistent results when applied to the same sample under similar conditions.

2.3 Statistical Description of Personal Characteristics:

The personal characteristics of the survey respondents can be represented as follows:

Table (2) Frequency distribution by gender

Gender categories	Frequency	Percentage
male	33	41.3
female	47	58.8
total	80	100

Source: Prepared by researchers using SPSS

Table (2) shows that the majority of the sample of private school principals in Erbil are female (58.8%), while males constitute (41.3%) of the total sample of (80) participants. This indicates that women represent a larger percentage

within the study sample, reflecting a clear participation of women in administrative positions in private schools within the city.

Table (3) Frequency distribution by age group

age group	Frequency	Percentage
Under 30 years old	8	10.0
31-40	41	51.3
41-50	19	23.8
More than 50 years	12	15.0
total	80	100

Source: Prepared by researchers using SPSS

Table (3) shows that the most represented age group among private school principals in Erbil is the 31–40 age group, representing 51.3% of the total sample, followed by the 41–50 age group at 23.8%, then the 50+ age group at 15.0%, while the least represented group was those under 30

years old at 10.0%. This indicates that the majority of participants belong to the middle age group, a stage in which a combination of practical experience and the ability to effectively perform administrative roles is expected.

Table (4) Frequency distribution according to academic achievement

academic achievement	Frequency	Percentage
Diploma	1	1.3
Bachelor's Degree	66	82.5
Higher Diploma	2	2.5
Master's Degree	10	12.5
Doctorate	1	1.3
total	80	100

Source: Prepared by researchers using SPSS

“The Role of Organizational Culture in Enhancing Administrative Performance among School Principals: An Analytical Study of the Opinions of a Sample of Private School Principals in Erbil”

Table (4) shows that the vast majority of private school principals in Erbil hold a bachelor's degree (82.5%), followed by those with a master's degree (12.5%), and then a higher diploma (2.5%). The percentages of those holding a doctorate

and a diploma were equally low (1.3% each). This indicates that the most common academic qualification among the sample is a bachelor's degree, with a limited number holding postgraduate degrees.

Table (5) Frequency distribution according to years of administrative experience in the school

administrative experience	Frequency	Percentage
Under 5 years	16	20.0
5-10 years	46	57.5
11-15 years	9	11.3
Over 15 years	9	11.3
total	80	100

Source: Prepared by researchers using SPSS

Table (5) shows that the majority of private school principals in Erbil have between 5 and 10 years of administrative experience, representing 57.5% of the total sample. This is followed by those with less than 5 years of experience, at 20.0%. The remaining percentages are equally distributed between those with 11-15 years of experience and those with more than 15 years of experience, at 11.3% each. This

indicates that most members of the sample possess moderate experience in the administrative field, which may contribute to achieving a balance between practical experience and the ability to keep pace with the demands of educational and administrative work.

Table (6) Frequency distribution according to years of experience in the field of education

experience in the field of education	Frequency	Percentage
Under 5 years	9	11.3
5-10 years	21	26.3
11-15 years	24	30.0
16-20 years	10	12.5
21-25 years	7	8.8
Over 25 years	9	11.3
total	80	100

Source: Prepared by researchers using SPSS

Table (6) shows that the most represented age group among private school principals in Erbil, in terms of years of experience in education, is the 11–15 year age group (30.0%), followed by the 5–10 year age group (26.3%), and then the 16–20 year age group (12.5%). The least represented age group was the 21–25 year age group (8.8%), while the less than 5 year age group and the more than 21 year age group each had 11.3%. This indicates that most participants possess moderate to long years of teaching experience, reflecting their established expertise in the field of education and their ability to perform their administrative duties efficiently.

3.3 Analysis of Study Themes and Hypotheses:

This research presents a comprehensive analytical study of the study's themes to understand their reality within the target research community. The following is a detailed presentation of the results, clarifying the main themes and hypotheses upon which the study was based, and demonstrating their relevance to the studied community and the relationships between them. The most important statistical and analytical indicators will be presented, reflecting an accurate picture of the phenomenon under investigation. This will be accompanied by an evaluation of the validity of the previously formulated hypotheses and an interpretation of the

“The Role of Organizational Culture in Enhancing Administrative Performance among School Principals: An Analytical Study of the Opinions of a Sample of Private School Principals in Erbil”

extracted results in light of the theoretical framework and relevant previous studies.

First Hypothesis: Null Hypothesis (H0): There is no statistically significant positive correlation between organizational culture and administrative performance at a significance level of 0.05. Alternative Hypothesis (H1): There is a statistically significant positive correlation between organizational culture and administrative performance at a significance level of 0.05.

Table (7) shows a moderately strong positive correlation between organizational culture and administrative

performance, with a Pearson correlation coefficient of 0.577 at a significance level of 0.000 (Sig = 0.000), which is less than the required significance level of 0.05. This indicates that the relationship between the two variables is statistically significant. Based on this result, the null hypothesis (H0), which states that there is no relationship, is rejected, and the alternative hypothesis (H1), which confirms the existence of a statistically significant positive correlation between organizational culture and administrative performance among private school principals in Erbil, is accepted.

Table (7) Pearson's correlation coefficient between the two variables

Variables		Organizational culture	Administrative performance
Organizational culture	Pearson correlation coefficient	1	.577**
	p-value		0.000
Administrative performance	Pearson correlation coefficient	.577**	
	p-value	0.000	

Source: Prepared by researchers using SPSS

Second Hypothesis: The null hypothesis (H0): There is no statistically significant positive correlation between the dimensions of organizational culture and administrative performance at a significance level of 0.05.

Alternative Hypothesis (H1): There is a statistically significant positive correlation between the dimensions of organizational culture and administrative performance at a significance level of 0.05.

Table (8) shows the existence of positive and significant correlations between the dimensions of organizational culture and the dimensions of administrative performance. The correlation coefficient between teamwork and decision-making reached 0.306** at a significance level of 0.006, and between norms, rules, direction, and control reached 0.353**

at a significance level of 0.000. A relatively strong correlation also appeared between innovation, creativity, planning, and organization (0.638**) at a significance level of 0.000. Since all Sig values are less than 0.05, the relationships between the dimensions are statistically significant.

Based on these results, the null hypothesis (H0), which states that there is no relationship, is rejected, and the alternative hypothesis (H1), which confirms the existence of a positive and significant correlation between the dimensions of organizational culture and the dimensions of administrative performance among private school principals in Erbil, is accepted.

Table (8) Pearson's correlation coefficient between the two variable dimensions

Correlation between the two variables	Pearson correlation coefficient	p-value
Teamwork - Decision-Making	.306**	0.006
Norms and Rules - Directing and Controlling	.353**	0.000
Innovation and Creativity - Planning and Organizing	.638**	0.000

Source: Prepared by researchers using SPSS

Third Hypothesis: The Null Hypothesis (H0): Organizational culture does not have a statistically significant positive effect on administrative performance at a significance level of 0.05. Alternative Hypothesis (H1): Organizational culture has a statistically significant positive effect on administrative performance at a significance level of 0.05.

Table (9) shows the results of the simple linear regression analysis to measure the effect of organizational culture (independent variable) on administrative performance (dependent variable). The results showed that the regression coefficient for organizational culture was 0.643, with a t-value of 6.233 at a significance level of 0.000, which is less

“The Role of Organizational Culture in Enhancing Administrative Performance among School Principals: An Analytical Study of the Opinions of a Sample of Private School Principals in Erbil”

than 0.05. This indicates that the effect of organizational culture on administrative performance is statistically significant and positive. The F-value was 38.855 at a significance level of 0.000, confirming the statistical strength of the model. The coefficient of determination (R^2) was 0.333, meaning that organizational culture explains 33.3% of the changes in administrative performance, while the

remaining percentage is attributed to other factors not included in the model.

Based on these results, the null hypothesis (H_0) is rejected, and the alternative hypothesis (H_1) is accepted, which states that organizational culture has a positive and significant impact on the administrative performance of private school principals in Erbil.

Table (9) Models of the effect of an independent variable on a dependent variable

Dependent variable: Administrative performance	Regression coefficients	values-t	p-values	F	p-values	Coefficient of determination
Fixed value	1.326	2.846	0.006	38.855	0.000	0.333
Organizational culture	0.643	6.233	0.000			

Source: Prepared by researchers using SPSS

Fourth Hypothesis: The null hypothesis (H_0): The dimensions of organizational culture do not have a significant positive impact on administrative performance at a significance level of 0.05.

Alternative Hypothesis (H_1): The dimensions of organizational culture do have a significant positive impact on administrative performance at a significance level of 0.05.

Table 10 shows the results of the linear regression analysis measuring the impact of organizational culture dimensions on administrative performance. The results showed that all three dimensions have a significant positive impact on administrative performance at a significance level of 0.05.

- The teamwork dimension achieved a regression coefficient of 0.427, with a t-value of 4.456 and a p-value of 0.000, and a coefficient of determination ($R^2 = 0.203$). This means it explains approximately 20.3% of the variance in administrative performance.

- The norms and rules dimension had a regression coefficient of 0.390, a t-value of 3.894, and a sigmoid coefficient of 0.000, along with a coefficient of determination ($R^2 = 0.163$), explaining 16.3% of the variance.

- The innovation and creativity dimension had the highest impact, with a regression coefficient of 0.451, a t-value of 5.778, and a sigmoid coefficient of 0.000, along with a coefficient of determination ($R^2 = 0.300$), explaining 30.0% of the variance in administrative performance.

These results indicate that all three dimensions positively and significantly influence administrative performance, but the innovation and creativity dimension had the greatest impact compared to the other dimensions. Therefore, the null hypothesis (H_0) is rejected, and the alternative hypothesis (H_1) is accepted, stating that the dimensions of organizational culture positively and significantly influence the administrative performance of private school principals in Erbil.

Table (10) Models of the effect of the dimensions of an independent variable on a dependent variable

Dependent variable: Administrative performance	Regression coefficients	values-t	values-P	F	values-P	Coefficient of determination
Fixed value	2.279	5.213	0.000	19.858	0.000	0.203
Teamwork	0.427	4.456	0.000		0.000	
Fixed value	2.487	5.565	0.000	15.163	0.000	0.163
Norms and Rules	0.390	3.894	0.000		0.000	
Norms and Rules	2.182	6.150	0.000	33.382	0.000	0.300
Innovation and Creativity	0.451	5.778	0.000		0.000	

Source: Prepared by researchers using SPSS

4. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

1.4 Conclusions

1. Women represent a larger percentage of the study sample, reflecting a clear participation of women in administrative positions in private schools within the city.
2. The majority of participants belong to the middle-aged age group, a stage in which a combination of practical experience and the ability to effectively perform administrative roles is expected.
3. Most members of the sample possess moderate experience in the administrative field, which may contribute to achieving a balance between practical experience and the ability to keep pace with the demands of educational and administrative work.
4. Most participants possess moderate to extensive teaching experience, reflecting the depth of their expertise in the educational field and their ability to perform their administrative duties efficiently.
5. There is a positive and significant correlation between organizational culture and administrative performance among private school principals in Erbil.
6. There is a positive and significant correlation between the dimensions of organizational culture and the dimensions of administrative performance among private school principals in Erbil.
7. The dimensions of organizational culture have a positive and significant impact on the administrative performance of private school principals in Erbil.

2.4 Recommendations

Based on the findings, the study recommends the following:

1. Raising awareness and knowledge among administrators and staff about the importance of the prevailing organizational culture in the school and how it directly impacts administrative performance and educational outcomes.
2. Encouraging administrators to identify the prevailing culture in their schools and work to develop it into a culture that supports creativity, teamwork, accountability, and initiative.
3. Conducting specialized and ongoing training courses and workshops for school administrators that focus on how to build and manage a positive and effective organizational culture.
5. Encouraging administrative decentralization within schools and enhancing the participation of teachers and administrators in decision-making (especially decisions related to the educational process); this fosters a culture of trust and ownership and motivates performance.
6. Providing a platform for open dialogue within the school to exchange ideas and accept differing opinions as a cornerstone of a healthy organizational culture.

7. Establishing a system of incentives and rewards (both tangible and intangible) that clearly and directly links the outstanding administrative performance of administrators and teachers to the positive organizational culture they successfully cultivate.
8. Adopt clear mechanisms for the work of teams within schools in addressing problems and developing curricula, which promotes a culture of cooperation and shared responsibility instead of an individualistic or bureaucratic culture.

REFERENCES

1. Abbas, M. Faisal Dhiab, (2022), The Impact of Organizational Culture on Human Resources Performance Practices: A Field Study in Sayel and Al-Dawra for Grain Trading – Baghdad, Published Graduation Research Project, Iraqi University, College of Administration and Economics, Department of Business Administration, Iraq.
2. Abukush, A. Rizq, (2024), The Level of Organizational Culture Prevailing in Negev Primary Schools from the Teachers' Perspective, Educational Journal, Volume (38), Issue (150), pp. 169-196.
3. Ahbeil, A. Raheel, Abuqasim, M. Hussein, and Al-Sadiq, A. Muhammad (2022), Organizational Culture and its Relationship to Administrative Practices among Secondary School Principals from the Teachers' Perspective: A Field Study, Bachelor's Thesis, Published, University of Sebha, Faculty of Arts - Department of Educational Planning and Administration.
4. Ahmed, A. Rouhi, and Abu Hussein, A. Muhammad, (2022), The Impact of Organizational Commitment on the Quality of Electronic Services with Organizational Learning as a Mediating Variable among Foreign Commercial Banks Operating in Jordan, Arab Journal of Science and Research Publication, Journal of Economic, Administrative, and Legal Sciences, Volume (6), Issue (6), pp. 89-115.
5. Ahmed, S. J., & Ibrahim, H. R. (2022). Towards Directing Agricultural Graduates to Small Agricultural Projects. Journal of historical & cultural studies an academic magazine, 13(56).
6. Al-Afad, A. Ali Hadi, and Al-Najjar, A. Ali Saleh, (2022), Requirements for Developing Administrative Performance among Secondary School Principals in Sana'a in Light of the Administrative Creativity Approach, Al-Andalus Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences, Volume (9), Issue (52), pp. 34-68.
7. Al-Ahmadi, F. Lafi Musfir, (2018), Performance Management Strategies for Primary School Principals in Madinah, Published Master's Thesis,

“The Role of Organizational Culture in Enhancing Administrative Performance among School Principals: An Analytical Study of the Opinions of a Sample of Private School Principals in Erbil”

- Journal of Scientific Research in Education, Issue (19), pp. 428-454.
8. Al-Akouri, S. Abdullah, (2024), The Role of Information Technology in Improving the Administrative Performance of Principals of Schools in Qasr Bin Ghashir from Their Perspective and that of Their Assistants, *Journal of Educational Sciences, Al-Asmariya Islamic University, College of Education, Volume (5), Issue (1), pp. 457-481.*
 9. Alian, D. Abdul Ali, (2012), *Organizational Culture and Administrative Practices among Public School Principals and the Relationship between Them from the Perspective of Teachers in the Jerusalem and Ramallah and Al-Bireh Governorates*, Published Master's Thesis, An-Najah National University, Faculty of Graduate Studies, Nablus, Palestine.
 10. Al-Murikhi, M. bint Hazza, (2023), *Improving the Administrative Performance of Secondary School Principals in Hafr Al-Batin Governorate in Light of Artificial Intelligence Requirements*, *Journal of the Arabian Peninsula Center for Educational and Humanistic Research, Volume (2), Issue (17), pp. 66-95.*
 11. Al-Otaibi, S. Majid, (2014), *Organizational Culture and its Relationship to the Value System of Secondary School Principals in Kuwait from the Teachers' Perspective*, Published Master's Thesis, Middle East University, College of Educational Sciences, Department of Administration and Curriculum, Amman, Jordan.
 12. Al-Shammari, a. Abed, and Al-Anzi, H. bint Ali, (2022), *Organizational Culture and its Relationship to Organizational Behavior among Female Secondary School Teachers in Hafr Al-Batin*, *Umm Al-Qura University Journal of Educational and Psychological Sciences, Volume (14), Issue (4), pp. 179-203.*
 13. Bahis, J. Muhammad, (2022), *The Role of Administrative Control in Developing the Administrative Performance of Public-School Principals in South Hebron from Their Perspective*, *Journal of Educational and Psychological Sciences, Volume (6), Issue (48), pp. 52-74.*
 14. Bin H. Al-Laithi, Muhammad B. Ali, (2008), *The Organizational Culture of the School Principal and Its Role in Administrative Creativity from the Perspective of Primary School Principals in the Holy City of Makkah*, Published Master's Thesis, Umm Al-Qura University, College of Education, Department of Educational Administration and Planning, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia.
 15. Fadel, A. Abbas, (2023), *Organizational Culture and its Relationship to the Administrative Organization of School Principals from the Teachers' Perspective*, *Anbar University Journal of Physical and Sports Sciences, Volume (14), Issue (27), pp. 391-401.*
 16. Haidar, R. Atiya, (2024), *A proposed educational vision for developing administrative performance in basic education schools in Zliten*, *Journal of Educational Sciences, Faculty of Education - Al-Asmariya Islamic University, Volume (5), Issue (1), pp. 502-518.*
 17. Hassanin, N. Ibrahim Al-Desouki Ramadan, Abdulrasoul, M. Abu Al-Nour, and Eid, M. Omar Ahmed, (2022), *Developing the administrative performance of principals in the second cycle of basic education in light of an international standard*, *Fayoum University Journal of Educational and Psychological Sciences, Volume (16), Issue (9), pp. 1010-1049.*
 18. Ibrahim, H. R. & Ahmed, H. I., 2025. *Economic Violence against Women and its Impact on Family Disintegration (An analytical study of the opinions of a sample of women in women's shelter centers - Erbil)*. *ZANCO Journal of Human Sciences, 29(2), pp. 56-80.*
 19. Ibrahim, H. R., 2025. *Between Policy and Practice: Understanding University Leadership Decision-Making in Politically Shared Systems in the Kurdistan Region-Iraq*. *University of Kirkuk Journal for Administrative and Economic Science, 15 (3) Part (2): 220-237*
 20. Ibrahim, H.R. and Ahmed, H.I., 2023. *The Role of Civilization Management in Social Life-Analytical Research (Economic, Administration and Cultural) in Erbil City*. *Iraqi Journal of Humanitarian, Social and Scientific Research, 3(8S).*
 21. Ibrahim, H.R. and Omer, T.Q., 2024. *The Role of Air Transportation in Importing Gold for the Year 2024 in the City of Erbil*. *Zanco Journal of Human Sciences, 28(5).*
 22. Ibrahim, H.R. and Wali, A.I., 2022. *The Role of Knowledge Economy in Achieving Strategic Success: Analytical study of the opinions of department heads in a sample of Colleges of Salahaddin University-Erbil*. *Zanco Journal of Human Sciences, 26(4), pp.178-194.*
 23. Kamel, J. Hatem, (2019), *The Reality of Administrative Performance According to Hallinger's Criterion and its Relationship to Administrative Excellence among Secondary School Principals*, *Al-Ustad Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences, Special Issue for the Seventh Scientific Conference, pp. 39-74.*
 24. Marqatan, M. Musa, (2020), *Ethical Leadership and its Relationship to Organizational Culture among*

“The Role of Organizational Culture in Enhancing Administrative Performance among School Principals: An Analytical Study of the Opinions of a Sample of Private School Principals in Erbil”

Public Secondary School Principals in Zarqa Governorate from the Teachers' Perspective, Published Master's Thesis, Middle East University, Faculty of Educational Sciences, Department of Administration and Curriculum, Amman, Jordan.

25. Muqabala, R. Muhammad, (2022), Organizational Culture and Its Relationship to Administrative Practices Among School Principals from the Teachers' Perspective, *Journal of Scientific Research and Publication*, Assiut University, Faculty of Education, Volume (38), Issue (9), pp. 197-212.
26. Musallaha, A.M., and Al-Sharman, M. M., (2024), The Level of Organizational Culture Prevailing Among Primary School Principals Within the Green Line and Its Relationship to Developing Creative Behavior Among Teachers, *Jordanian Educational Journal*, Jordanian Association for Educational Sciences, Volume (9), Issue (1), pp. 76-101.
27. Omar, N. Musa, (2024), The prevailing organizational culture in Arab preparatory and secondary schools within the Green Line from the teachers' perspective and its relationship to their use of violence against students: Examining job burnout as a mediating variable, PhD dissertation, published, Arab American University, College of Graduate Studies, Department of Educational Sciences, Palestine.
28. Salah, M. Taher M., (2024), Measuring and Evaluating the Administrative Performance of Palestinian Schools and Educational Institutions (Governmental and Private) in Light of the CITA Model for School Accreditation and Quality Assurance, from the Perspective of School Principals and their Deputies (A Case Study of Nablus Governorate), *Journal of Arts, Literature, Humanities and Social Sciences*, Volume (113), Issue (113), pp. 128-156.
29. Salh.D.M.Ibrahim.H.R.Jameel.D.I. (2018). Use six Sigma technique to configure the plate ratio of defective units for quality control and compare them with plate ratio of defective units using three Sigma with the application. *Qalaai Zanist Journal*, 3(4), 756-772.
30. Wali, P.D.A.I. and Ibrahim, H.R., 2022. The Role of Knowledge Economy Indicators in Achieving Entrepreneurial Performance Analytical of the opinions of a sample of small project managers in Erbil City. *JOURNAL OF HISTORICAL & CULTURAL STUDIES* an academic magazine, 13(53/1)